

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORT - THE BASIS FOR FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract: *This article examines the attitude of people to the formation of a healthy image life. In the article, the phenomenon of a healthy lifestyle is presented as a specific form expedient human activity - activities aimed at preserving, strengthening and improving his health. Attention is focused on the side of physical activity and the desire to her choice of food and a responsible attitude to the formation of dietary habits. In the work also shows the possibilities for people in the field of physical activity. The positive influence from the outside on the attitude to a healthy lifestyle is considered.*

Keywords— healthy lifestyle, health, beauty, physical culture.

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions of development of Uzbekistan, the issues of strengthening the spiritual and physical health of citizens, the formation of a healthy lifestyle (HLS) are of particular importance. In this regard, close attention to physical culture and sports as an inseparable part of public culture is becoming a priority in the social policy of the state. The urgency of these problems was repeatedly pointed out in his speeches by the President of the Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. Thus, in his message to the Oliy Majlis, the President noted that “our task is to attract the maximum number of citizens to physical culture and sports, to form and strengthen the values of a healthy lifestyle in society” [1]. A.V. Tsarik, V.V. Borisov, O.V. Ustinova, L.N. Bibik and others write about this convincingly in their works. However, the level of mass physical culture and sports throughout the country remains very low. The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that a significant part of young people does not pay due attention to physical education and sports. Researchers note that young people do not correlate a healthy lifestyle with the ability to lead a full-fledged life activity. The value of "sports and physical education" occupies only 11th position in the rating, giving way to "big money", "life without conflicts", etc. Young people believe that health is a genetically inherent characteristic and physical education and sports will not affect their health in any way. At the same time, only 34% of respondents clearly understand the meaning of the concept of “healthy lifestyle”. The rest either have a vague idea about him, or did not ask this question at all. It is a shame that the indicator “engaging in physical culture and sports” is inferior to such types of pastime as “surfing the Internet” and “watching TV” [2: 93–94]. The basis for the formation of a healthy lifestyle is the personal and motivational attitude of a given person to the embodiment of his social, physical, intellectual and mental abilities and capabilities.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A healthy lifestyle is a way of life, aimed at preserving and improving people's health, as a condition and prerequisite for the existence and development of other aspects of the way of life. A healthy lifestyle is all that has a beneficial effect on his health and, above all, systematic physical education and sports. A healthy lifestyle contributes to the preservation and strengthening of health and is the basis for the prevention of most diseases. According to a number of domestic and foreign researchers, the health of the population more than 50% depends on the way of life [3: 102]. Physical culture is a part of social culture in which the processes of assimilation and reproduction of social experience by a person are realized. With the formation and development of social educational and educational systems, modern physical culture and sports acquire the status of a dominant factor in the formation and development of physical qualities, skills and abilities of a person. The sphere of physical culture and sports in this status should be the basis for the formation of a healthy lifestyle and is presented as a subsystem of vital activity associated with the development of a person's physical and spiritual capabilities to achieve their perfection. A healthy lifestyle program in this aspect is a comprehensive program for the formation of knowledge, goals, personal guidelines and norms of behavior that ensure the preservation and strengthening of physical and mental health as one of the value components that contribute to cognitive and emotional development at the initial stage of general education.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As you know, the main elements of physical culture, as a component of a healthy lifestyle, are: physique culture, health culture and motor culture. Researchers identify the main indicators of personal physical culture: 1) a person's attitude to his health as a value, the degree of manifestation of this attitude; 2) the nature of this relationship (arbitrary or declarative); 3) the means used to preserve and strengthen health, the ability to use them; 4) the level of knowledge about the physical condition, means and methods of maintaining and

strengthening health, health in accordance with social norms, ideals, models; 5) the desire to provide all possible help to other people in activities for health improvement and physical improvement. In physical culture, in addition to knowledge and psychological attitude to maintaining a healthy lifestyle, includes the means used to maintain and strengthen health (for example, exercise, sports, etc.), as well as the skills to use them. A systematic approach to the formation of health and healthy lifestyle values at the stages of primary, secondary and higher education should be based on the factors influencing the health of the younger generation and the country's youth. These factors are:

- unfavorable social, economic and environmental conditions;
- risk factors that take place in educational institutions, leading to a further deterioration in the health of children, adolescents and youth from the first to the last year of schooling;
- complexes of knowledge, attitudes, rules of behavior, habits actively formed at primary school age;
- peculiarities of the attitude of primary school students to their health, which is associated with the lack of experience of "ill health" in children (except for children with serious chronic diseases) and the child's perception of the state of the disease mainly as a restriction of freedom, inability to predict the consequences of their attitude to health.

These factors are characterized by universal (general) and unique (specific) properties for each village, city, district, region, region. The task of the researcher is to determine the specific properties of healthy lifestyle formation for a specific educational system based on the physical culture of sports. In the tasks of forming a culture of a healthy lifestyle of students, we propose the following aspects of activity:

- to form an idea of the positive factors affecting health;
- teach students to consciously choose actions, behavior that allow them to maintain and strengthen their health;
- teach to follow the rules of personal hygiene and develop readiness based on its use to independently maintain their health;
- to form an idea of correct (healthy) nutrition, its regime, useful products;
- to form an idea of the rational organization of the daily routine, study and rest, physical activity, to teach the child to compose, analyze and control his daily routine;
- give an idea, taking into account the principle of information security, about negative risk factors for children's health (reduced physical activity, infectious diseases, overwork, etc.), about the existence and causes of dependence on tobacco, alcohol, drugs and other psychoactive substances, their harmful effects on health;

- to give an idea of the impact of positive and negative emotions on health, including those obtained from communicating with a computer, watching TV, participating in gambling;

- teach elementary skills of emotional unloading (relaxation);

- to form skills of positive communicative communication;

- to form an idea of the main components of a culture of health and a healthy lifestyle;

- to form the child's need to fearlessly consult a doctor on any health issues, including those related to the characteristics of growth and development. The formation of a healthy lifestyle presupposes the effective organization of physical culture and recreation activities of educational institutions, taking into account the specifics of the local area.

4. CONCLUSION

It should be aimed at ensuring the rational organization of the motor regime of students, normal physical development and motor readiness of students of all ages, increasing the adaptive capabilities of the body, maintaining and strengthening the health of students and the formation of a culture of health and includes:

- full-fledged and high-quality work with students of all health groups (at physical education lessons, in sections, etc.);

- rational and appropriate organization of physical culture lessons and active motor activities at the level of primary general education;

- organization of dynamic changes, physical education minutes in the classroom, contributing to emotional relief and increased physical activity;

- regular sports and recreational activities (days of sports, competitions, Olympiads, hikes, etc.). The implementation of this activity depends on the administrations of educational institutions, physical education teachers, medical workers, as well as all teachers.

5. REFERENCES

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